

Future healthcare professionals' knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding antibiotic use and resistance in Iraq

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Abstract

Antimicrobial resistance is a fatal health crisis imposing a significant clinical and economic burden. A cross-sectional questionnaire-based survey was submitted through social media platforms to medical and pharmacy students in Iraq from July to August 2025. Among 394 students from 13 universities, pharmacy students constituted 70.8% of the sample. Overall, 58.1% demonstrated adequate knowledge, and 56.1% demonstrated a positive attitude. However, 60.2% practiced self-medication, and a significant proportion believed that antibiotics are effective for treating the common cold (29.9%) and sore throat (63.7%). Furthermore, only 43.7% were familiar with the term antimicrobial stewardship. GPA and avoidance of self-medication were key predictors of adequate knowledge. Study year was a predictor of adequate knowledge and positive attitude, while satisfaction with antimicrobial education significantly predicted attitude and self-medication practice. A curriculum review to integrate the core principles of antimicrobial stewardship is warranted to prepare highly skilled healthcare professionals and prevent a further rise in antimicrobial resistance.

Keywords

Antimicrobial resistance, education, healthcare students, Iraq, knowledge

Introduction

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) poses a significant threat to public health when pathogens develop specific mechanisms to evade the inhibitory effects of antimicrobials, rendering them ineffective (Ahmed et al. 2024). The incidence of multidrug-resistant pathogens is increasing, and low- and middle-income countries are disproportionately affected (Lubwama et al. 2021). AMR compromises the effectiveness of first-line, cost-effective antibiotics, mandating the use of costly second- and third-line medications, leading to prolonged hospital stays, increased risk of complications, and higher healthcare costs (Homsy et al. 2025). According to global estimates, AMR was responsible for

1.2 million deaths in 2021, and without proper actions, the death toll is expected to reach 10 million by 2050 (Ahmed et al. 2024). Given the complexity of the consequences of AMR, the World Health Organization (WHO) adopted a global action plan framework to contain antibiotic resistance, which was subsequently adopted by countries worldwide (Iwu and Patrick 2021). In addition, the WHO has established World Antibiotic Awareness Week (WAAW) from 18 to 24 November each year to raise awareness of antimicrobial resistance and promote prudent antibiotic use.

Excessive and irrational use of antibiotics is the main driver of antibiotic resistance, especially in inpatient set-

tings where broad-spectrum antibiotics are widely prescribed (Nassr OA et al. 2018). In addition, in developing countries, 62% of antibiotics are purchased from community pharmacies without a prescription (Auta et al. 2019). Furthermore, antimicrobial stewardship, an intervention to address antibiotic resistance, is not well implemented in Middle Eastern countries (Borg et al. 2008).

Healthcare providers, including doctors and pharmacists, are the frontline stewards of appropriate antibiotic use and the fight against AMR. The physician prescribes the antibiotic, and the pharmacist dispenses it and educates patients on proper use. Interdisciplinary collaboration to promote appropriate use is essential to enhance clinical outcomes and prevent further increases in resistance (Homsy et al. 2025). Despite their best efforts, 20–50% of antibiotic prescriptions in primary care are deemed inappropriate (Alshehri and Khawagi 2025). In addition, 55% of antibiotics are prescribed unnecessarily for viral respiratory tract infections such as the common cold (Abuawad et al. 2024). The problem was further exacerbated during the COVID-19 pandemic, with only 8% of antibiotic prescriptions appropriately prescribed (Majumder et al. 2020). Studies indicate that antibiotic knowledge affects prescribing behavior, and healthcare students begin developing their clinical skills during training (Silverberg et al. 2017). Thus, prospective healthcare professionals need to be equipped with sufficient education and training in appropriate antibiotic use to reduce morbidity, mortality, and healthcare costs associated with AMR (Silverberg et al. 2017; Majumder et al. 2020).

Education of healthcare staff is one of the core pillars of antimicrobial stewardship for mitigating resistance (Majumder et al. 2020). University education plays an important role in shaping perceptions and attitudes toward antibiotic use (Silverberg et al. 2017; Alshehri and Khawagi 2025). Insufficient knowledge among healthcare professionals leads to inappropriate use, thereby contributing to antibiotic resistance (Silverberg et al. 2017). Studies suggest knowledge gaps regarding the responsible use of antibiotics among undergraduate healthcare students. For example, a recent study among final-year medical and pharmacy students in Saudi Arabia indicates that only 44.7% have good knowledge of antibiotics, and this figure is even lower in East Africa (36.6%) (Lubwama et al. 2021; Alshehri and Khawagi 2025). Similarly, in Nepal, half of medical students self-medicate with antibiotics to manage symptoms of the common cold, such as rhinorrhea, sneezing, and sore throat (Mandal et al. 2020). In addition, only one-third of pharmacy students in Sudan demonstrate competence in interpreting microbiological reports (Abdelkarim et al. 2024).

In Iraq, alarming figures of AMR, including resistance to end-line antibiotics such as meropenem, have been reported, as well as irrational antibiotic use in hospital and community settings (Nassr OA et al. 2018; Al-Jumaili and Ahmed 2024). Despite this, studies exploring healthcare students' knowledge regarding antibiotic use and resistance in Iraq are scarce. Therefore, we sought to evaluate the knowledge, attitudes, and practice of medical and

pharmacy students regarding antibiotic use and resistance, making this the first national, comprehensive study to provide insight into this topic and to inform targeted educational interventions to mitigate resistance.

Materials and methods

Study design and participants

A cross-sectional survey was administered to medical and pharmacy students via an online questionnaire in Iraq from July to August 2025. Eligible students were those who had completed basic science courses, including physiology, anatomy, pathology, medical microbiology, and pharmacology. Accordingly, fourth-, fifth-, and sixth-year medical students, and fourth- and fifth-year pharmacy students, were included, specifically those who had begun clinical training. This study was conducted and reported in line with STROBE guidelines (Cuschieri 2019).

Research instrument development

The tool was developed based on a literature review of similar studies. The researchers added additional questions to align with the study population, study objectives, and the national educational curriculum.

The questionnaire form consisted of six parts. Part one includes demographic information (age, sex, study major, study year, grade point average (GPA), and whether the student has a family member working in a health profession) (6 items). Part two refers to students' knowledge of antibiotic use and resistance. This part comprised 13 questions, and responses included True, False, or I do not know. The questions evaluated students' understanding of the basic principles of antimicrobial therapy, including culture and sensitivity testing, mechanisms of action (time- versus concentration-dependent killing), use in pregnancy, the association between excessive use, premature discontinuation, and development of resistance, and efficacy in viral infections such as the common cold. The knowledge score was calculated by assigning 1 point for each correct answer and 0 for incorrect or I do not know responses, resulting in a total score ranging from 0 to 13.

Part three refers to students' attitude toward antibiotic use and resistance and included seven questions with the possibility of answering yes or no. This part evaluated students' agreement on whether hospital admission increases the risk of nosocomial infections, whether dosing of the same antibiotic can differ depending on the type of infection, extended duration of treatment for certain infections, such as endocarditis, familiarity with certain terms, such as intravenous/oral switch and antimicrobial stewardship, and whether self-medication contributes to resistance. The attitude score was estimated by assigning 1 point for each correct answer and 0 for incorrect responses. The final score ranged from 0 to 7.

Part four (1 item) evaluates the practice regarding the usual method of accessing antibiotics in the past year, and possible answers included prescription or self-medication.

Part five included four questions related to the perception of antimicrobial use and resistance with a binary response category of yes or no. This part assessed students' perception of certain issues, such as antimicrobial resistance as a public health concern, inadequate knowledge and antimicrobial resistance, excessive and inappropriate antibiotic use in Iraq, and the role of pharmacists in mitigating resistance. Part six includes two closed-ended questions assessing students' satisfaction with the quality of antimicrobial education and whether they require additional courses to strengthen their antibiotic knowledge. The survey took 5–10 minutes to complete.

Three dichotomous dependent variables were identified, including antibiotic knowledge level (adequate, inadequate), attitude status (positive, negative), and self-medication practice (yes, no). Categories of knowledge and attitude were created based on the median value of knowledge (10) and attitude (6) in line with a similar study (Horvat et al. 2022). The median is a statistical value that divides the data equally into two halves; thus, it captures the central distribution of knowledge and attitude scores among participants and can be considered a meaningful threshold. Participants were classified as having either adequate (≥ 11) or inadequate knowledge (< 11) and positive (≥ 6) or negative attitude (< 6).

Validity and reliability assessment of the questionnaire

Content validity was assessed by four academic experts holding a PhD in clinical pharmacy who qualitatively reviewed the questions for cultural relevance, appropriateness, and inclusiveness. In addition, to preliminarily assess the clarity and comprehensibility of the questions, a pilot study was conducted using 30 samples. Minor amendments were made to specific items. Piloted samples were excluded from the final analysis. Furthermore, the reliability of the scales assessing antibiotic knowledge and attitude was evaluated using Cronbach's alpha. The α -value of the 13-item knowledge scale was 0.63, and the 7-item attitude scale was 0.60, indicating moderate internal consistency. An alpha value lower than 0.7 is considered acceptable in knowledge, attitude, and practice research due to the multidimensional nature of the construct, limited number of items, and the dichotomous response format, which, unlike Likert scales, limits response variability, leading to lower Cronbach's α . Perception questions were designed to evaluate independent aspects of antibiotic use and were therefore analyzed individually rather than as a unified scale.

Data collection procedure

The instrument was developed using web-based survey software (Google Forms). Initially, the questionnaire was developed in English; then, a fluent bilingual academic pharmacist translated it into Arabic. The Arabic version was back-translated to English by a different academic pharmacist and compared with the original version to ensure that the conceptual meaning was retained during

translation (forward/back-translation). Questions were presented in both Arabic and English to improve comprehension. An invitation letter accompanied the questionnaire link and outlined the study objective, target population, and time required to complete the questionnaire, emphasizing that participation is voluntary and that confidentiality would be maintained.

The author, who is a lecturer at a pharmacy school, initially shared the questionnaire link with her pharmacy students and encouraged them to share the link with eligible peers (snowball sampling method). The questionnaire link was subsequently distributed to pharmacy and medical students through social media platforms, including Facebook, WhatsApp, and Telegram groups, as well as through student association groups. Despite these efforts, medical students' participation was limited.

Ethical consideration

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the institutional review board of the College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq (reference no. 201). Prior to participation, informed consent was obtained from all participants. The consent form explained the study's aims and objectives and informed students of the estimated time required to complete the survey, emphasizing that participation is voluntary and anonymous.

Statistical analysis

Data were presented as numbers and percentages of correct responses. In addition to descriptive statistics, the median (interquartile range) of the knowledge and attitude scales was also calculated. Responses were designed to be mandatory to avoid the possibility of missing data. Bivariate analysis using the Chi-square test was performed to test the association between dependent dichotomous variables, namely knowledge, attitude, and practice, with independent categorical variables such as sex, study year, study field, GPA, and satisfaction with antimicrobial education.

All variables with p -value < 0.05 in the bivariate analysis were entered into a multivariate logistic regression model to determine predictors independently associated with adequate knowledge, positive attitude, and antibiotic self-medication practice. Coding of dependent variables was as follows: knowledge (adequate = 1, inadequate = 0), attitude (positive = 1, negative = 0), and antibiotic self-medication practice (yes = 1, no = 0). All assumptions of the regression analysis for each model were met, and there was no evidence of multicollinearity measured by variance inflation factors (VIF) (all values were 1). The enter method was used, and the model fit well. The Hosmer and Lemeshow test for the knowledge, attitude, and practice model was not significant ($p = 0.486, 0.431, \text{ and } 0.838$, respectively). The results were presented as adjusted odds ratios (aOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI). Data were analyzed using IBM SPSS, and p -values of < 0.05 were considered significant.

Results

Sociodemographic characteristics of the study population

Among 394 students from 13 universities who participated in the study, pharmacy students accounted for 70.8% ($n = 279$) of the sample. There was a female predominance, constituting 73.1% ($n = 288$) of participants. The average age and range of the study population were 21.94 (20–36) years. Over half of participants (54.8%, $n = 216$) were fifth-year students, and the majority (60.9%, $n = 240$) had a medium or good GPA. Nearly half of the study sample (46.4%, $n = 183$) had a family member working in a healthcare environment (Table 1).

Table 1. Characteristics of the study population.

Characteristics	<i>n</i> (%)
Age, mean (S.D), range (years)	21.94 (1.59) (20-36)
20–21	161 (40.9)
22–23	197 (50.0)
≥24	36 (9.1)
Sex	
Male	106 (26.9)
Female	288 (73.1)
Study major	
Medicine	115 (29.2)
Pharmacy	279 (70.8)
Study year	
Fourth year	107 (27.2)
Fifth year	216 (54.8)
Sixth year	71 (18.0)
Grade point average (GPA)	
Satisfactory, failed	35 (8.9)
Medium, good	240 (60.9)
Very good, excellent	119 (30.2)
Family member working in the healthcare	
Yes	183 (46.4)
No	211 (53.6)

Knowledge of antibiotic use and resistance

The majority (58.1%, $n = 229$) had adequate knowledge. The median value of the knowledge score was 11, with an interquartile range of 10–12. The percentage of correct answers was > 80% for 10 out of 13 questions. Nearly all students (98.0%) agreed that excessive use of broad-spectrum antibiotics contributes to resistance. Most students (92.4%) believed that culture and sensitivity testing is recommended before commencing empiric antibiotic therapy in patients with systemic inflammatory response, and 89.6% agreed with switching to a narrow spectrum following empiric therapy with broad-spectrum antibiotics. Most were familiar with antibiotic adverse effects, including allergic reactions (88.8%), nephrotoxicity (83.5%), and *Clostridium difficile* superinfection (80.2%). In addition,

88.3% thought that premature discontinuation may contribute to resistance. In contrast, only 62.0% answered the question related to the time-dependent killing pattern of β -lactam and glycopeptides correctly. Furthermore, 29.9% and 63.7% of students incorrectly agreed that antibiotics are effective in the treatment of the common cold and sore throat, respectively (Table 2). In the bivariate analysis (Chi-square test), GPA ($p = 0.001$), study year ($p = 0.006$), satisfaction with antimicrobial education ($p = 0.043$), and self-medication ($p = 0.042$) were significantly associated with antibiotic knowledge.

Student's attitude and practice toward antibiotic use and resistance

Just more than half (56.1%; $n = 221$) had a positive attitude toward antibiotic use and resistance; median = 6, interquartile range (5–7). The majority (94.4%) agreed that hospital admission increases the risk of infections, and 87.1% believed that certain infections, such as endocarditis, require a prolonged course of antibiotic therapy. However, only 66.5% were familiar with the term intravenous/oral switch, and a lower percentage (43.7%) were familiar with the term antimicrobial stewardship. In the bivariate analysis, sex ($p = 0.016$), study year ($p = 0.000$), and satisfaction with the antimicrobial curriculum ($p = 0.000$) were associated with attitude.

With regard to practice, only 39.8% ($n = 157$) received antibiotics by prescription; the remainder (60.2%, $n = 237$) self-medicated, despite 94.7% believing that self-medication with antibiotics contributes to resistance (Table 3). In the bivariate analysis, self-medication practice was significantly associated with antibiotic knowledge ($p = 0.042$) and satisfaction with antimicrobial education ($p = 0.022$).

Perception of antibiotic use and resistance

Nearly all students (97.5%) agreed that antimicrobial resistance is a public health concern, and 98.0% thought that insufficient antibiotic knowledge contributes to resistance. In addition, 95.2% agreed that in Iraq, broad-spectrum antibiotics were unnecessarily prescribed for infections that would otherwise be resolved with narrow-spectrum antibiotics. The majority (96.7%) agreed on the role of the pharmacist in optimizing antibiotic use and minimizing the emergence of resistance (Table 4).

Students' satisfaction with antimicrobial education

Only 58.6% expressed satisfaction with the quality of antibiotic education received at schools, and the majority (96.4%) expressed a need for further antibiotic education (Table 5). Satisfaction with antimicrobial education was significantly associated with antibiotic knowledge ($p = 0.043$), sex ($p = 0.023$), and antibiotic self-medication practice ($p = 0.022$).

Table 2. Knowledge of antibiotic use and resistance.

#	Questions (Answers)	Correct n (%)	Incorrect/ unsure n (%)
1	Culture and sensitivity testing before commencing empiric antibiotic therapy is recommended in patients with systemic inflammatory response. (True)	364 (92.4)	30 (7.6)
2	Following empiric therapy with broad-spectrum antibiotics, de-escalation to narrow spectrum once culture and susceptibility testing results are known is advised. (True)	353 (89.6)	41 (10.4)
3	Allergy to antibiotics is one of the most common drug-related allergies (True)	350 (88.8)	44 (11.2)
4	Factors associated with failure of antibiotic therapy include inadequate dosing or duration, poor compliance, or drug interactions (True)	367 (93.1)	27 (6.8)
5	Aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, and metronidazole possess concentration-dependent bactericidal activity (True)	316 (80.2)	78 (19.8)
6	Betalactam and glycopeptides possess time-dependent bactericidal activity (True)	244 (62.0)	150 (38.0)
7	Quinolones and tetracyclines are contraindicated in pregnancy (True)	370 (93.9)	24 (6.1)
8	Coadministration of aminoglycoside antibiotics with vancomycin increases the risk of nephrotoxicity (True)	329 (83.5)	65 (16.5)
9	Excessive use of broad-spectrum antibiotics contributes to resistance (True)	386 (98.0)	8 (2.0)
10	Premature discontinuation of a prescribed course of antibiotics once the symptoms improve may contribute to resistance (True)	348 (88.3)	46 (11.7)
11	Broad-spectrum antibiotics increase the risk of secondary infections such as clostridium difficile infection. (True)	316 (80.2)	78 (19.8)
12	Antibiotics are effective in the treatment of cough and common cold (False)	276 (70.1)	118 (29.9)
13	Antibiotics are effective in the treatment of sore throats (False)	143 (36.3)	251 (63.7)

Predictors of antibiotic knowledge, attitude, and practice

According to multivariate logistic regression, predictors of adequate antibiotic knowledge included having a very good to excellent GPA (aOR = 3.98, 95% CI: 1.77–8.97). Another predictor was study year; students in the fifth year were more likely to have adequate antibiotic knowledge than fourth-year students (aOR = 2.60, 95% CI: 1.57–4.30). Similarly, those who avoided self-medication with antibiotics were more likely to have adequate knowledge (aOR = 1.61, 95% CI: 1.04–2.49).

Determinants of positive attitude included study year; students in the fifth year were more likely to have a positive attitude compared with fourth-year students (aOR = 2.35, 95% CI: 1.45–3.81). In addition, those who were satisfied with antimicrobial education were more likely to

Table 3. Students' attitudes and practices toward antibiotic use and resistance.

#	Questions (Answers)	Correct answers n (%)
Attitude		
1	Do you believe hospital admission increases risk of nosocomial infection with resistant pathogens? (Yes)	372 (94.4)
2	Do you think that the dosing regimen of the same antibiotic may be different depending on the type of infection? (Yes)	382 (97.0)
3	Do you think that double coverage with a similar spectrum of activity is justified in critically ill patients who are known to harbor resistant pathogens? (Yes)	273 (69.3)
4	Do you think that prostatitis, osteomyelitis, and endocarditis require a longer duration of antibiotic therapy (weeks to months)? (Yes)	343 (87.1)
5	Do you consider yourself familiar with the term antimicrobial stewardship? (Yes)	172 (43.7)
6	Do you consider yourself familiar with intravenous/oral switch of antibiotics? (Yes)	262 (66.5)
7	Do you agree that self-medication with antibiotics may lead to resistance? (Yes)	373 (94.7)
Practice		
1	Source of antibiotics used in the past year? (prescription)	157 (39.8)

Table 4. Students' perception regarding antibiotic use and resistance.

#	Questions (Answers)	Correct answers n (%)
1	Do you perceive antimicrobial resistance as a public health concern? (Yes)	384 (97.5)
2	Do you think insufficient knowledge about antibiotics contributes to antibiotic resistance? (Yes)	386 (98.0)
3	Do you believe that in Iraq, broad-spectrum antibiotics were overly used unnecessarily in infections that can be resolved with narrow-spectrum antibiotics? (Yes)	375 (95.2)
4	Do you think pharmacists, as a part of a multidisciplinary team, can improve use of antibiotics and minimize antibiotic resistance? (Yes)	381 (96.7)

Table 5. Students' satisfaction with antimicrobial courses taught at schools.

#	Questions	Responses	n (%)
1	Do you think you have received adequate knowledge on antibiotics and their appropriate use during your university education?	Yes	231 (58.6)
		No	163 (41.4)
2	Are you interested in learning more about antibiotic use and resistance?	Yes	380 (96.4)
		No	14 (3.6)

have a positive attitude than those who were not (aOR = 2.08, 95% CI: 1.37–3.17).

The only predictor of antibiotic self-medication practice was satisfaction with antimicrobial education; those who were dissatisfied with antimicrobial education were more likely to engage in self-medication practice (aOR = 1.57, 95% CI: 1.03–2.39) (Table 6).

Table 6. Multivariate logistic regression analysis of factors independently associated with students' knowledge, attitude, and self-medication practice.

Characteristics	Knowledge		Attitude		Self-medication practice	
	aOR (95% CI)	P-value	aOR (95% CI)	P-value	aOR (95% CI)	P-value
GPA		0.000				
Satisfactory	Reference		-	-	-	-
Moderate-good	1.45 (0.70-3.02)		-	-	-	-
Very good-excellent	3.98 (1.77-8.97)		-	-	-	-
Study year		0.002		0.002		
Fourth	Reference		Reference		-	-
Fifth	2.60 (1.57-4.30)		2.35 (1.45-3.81)		-	-
Sixth	2.24 (1.17-4.29)		2.42 (1.28-4.58)		-	-
Satisfaction with antimicrobial education				0.001		0.036
Yes	-	-	2.08 (1.37-3.17)		Reference	
No	-	-	Reference		1.57 (1.03-2.39)	
Self-medication practice		0.032				
Yes	Reference		-	-	-	-
No	1.61 (1.04-2.49)		-	-	-	-

aOR: adjusted odds ratio; CI: confidence interval; and GPA: grade point average

Discussion

The present study assessed the knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes of pharmacy and medical students in Iraq regarding antibiotic use and resistance. The predominance of female respondents (73.1%) and the lower participation of medical students (29.2%) observed in this study are in line with other international studies (Abuawad et al. 2024; Nukaly et al. 2024; Alshehri and Khawagi 2025; Homsy et al. 2025). The majority of students had adequate knowledge of antibiotic use and resistance (58.1%). The knowledge is comparable to that reported in the United Arab Emirates (56%) and Serbia (62.5%), but higher than that reported in Saudi Arabia (44.7%) and East Africa (36.6%) (Jairoun et al. 2019; Lubwama et al. 2021; Horvat et al. 2022; Alshehri and Khawagi 2025). Variations in knowledge levels may reflect differences in academic years, study tools, and curricula across countries. Despite these positive findings, only 43.7% were aware of the term antimicrobial stewardship; 63.7% and 29.9% thought that antibiotics can treat sore throat and the common cold, respectively; and 60.2% reported self-medication with antibiotics. In addition, only 58.6% attributed university education to enhancing their antibiotic knowledge, and the majority (96.4%) reported a need for further antimicrobial courses. GPA and avoidance of self-medication were key predictors of knowledge. Study year was a predictor of knowledge and attitude, while satisfaction with antimicrobial education significantly predicted attitude and self-medication practice.

While the majority demonstrated good antibiotic knowledge, a significant gap was evident in certain aspects. For example, 63.7% of respondents believed antibiotics can be used in the treatment of sore throat, while 29.9% thought that it can be helpful in treating the common cold; these figures are higher than those reported in Jordan, where 28.52% and 25.86% of medical, dental, and pharmacy students viewed antibiotics as effective for

cough or sore throat, respectively (Homsy et al. 2025). The findings align with a study in Saudi Arabia that found that 32.9% of medical students believed antibiotics were useful for the common cold (Nukaly et al. 2024). In Serbia, 85.1% of medical students believed that antibiotics are ineffective for treating the common cold (Horvat et al. 2022). In addition, self-medication was common among the study sample, despite their knowledge that this practice leads to antibiotic resistance, suggesting that greater knowledge does not always translate into better clinical practice. This is consistent with a similar study conducted in the United Arab Emirates, in which 38.2% of students reported self-medication (Jairoun et al. 2019). A similar study in Serbia reported a self-medication rate of 42.8% among medical, dental, and veterinary medicine students (Horvat et al. 2022). Self-medication is a common problem in Iraq, where antibiotics are often purchased without prescriptions (Al-Jumaili and Ahmed 2024). The national action plan to promote appropriate antibiotic use, including the prohibition on dispensing antibiotics without a prescription, is in place in Middle Eastern countries but is not well implemented (Homsy et al. 2025).

Furthermore, only 43.7% were familiar with the term antimicrobial stewardship, which is lower than that reported in Sudan (57.8%) but higher than that reported in Saudi Arabia (28.4%) and Iran (26.8%) (Abdelkarim et al. 2024; Kiani et al. 2024; Alshehri and Khawagi 2025). Antimicrobial stewardship involves a multidisciplinary team to promote responsible antibiotic use in inpatient and outpatient settings (Abdelkarim et al. 2024). The inclusion of the pharmacist in the clinical team is one of the seven pillars of antimicrobial stewardship (Majumder et al. 2020). They are involved in formulary and guideline development and in enhancing appropriate antibiotic use, including empirical therapy selection, dose adjustment, IV-to-oral switch, and therapeutic drug monitoring (Majumder et al. 2020; Abdelkarim et al. 2024; Homsy et al. 2025).

Multivariate binary logistic regression identified predictors associated with knowledge, attitude, and practice. Firstly, students with very good to excellent GPAs were nearly four times more likely to have adequate knowledge. Studies often use GPA as an indicator of academic performance. A similar study in Serbia found a significant association between students' GPAs and antibiotic knowledge (Horvat et al. 2022). In addition, a study in Korea indicated that GPA has predictive validity for clinical competence among medical graduates (Kim et al. 2016). Students with higher GPAs have developed discipline, study skills, and effective time-management strategies that contribute to critical thinking and problem-solving (Kim et al. 2016). During their studies, they have developed a deep foundational knowledge of pathology, microbiology, and pharmacology and often access high-quality resources to broaden their knowledge (Dejene et al. 2024). In addition, higher-GPA students tend to have greater awareness of public health issues, including antimicrobial resistance (Dejene et al. 2024). Another predictor of adequate antibiotic knowledge and positive attitude was study year, which is in line with other studies (Jairoun et al. 2019; Abuawad et al. 2024). Knowledge tends to increase with study year due to exposure to advanced courses of pharmacotherapy and infectious disease guidelines, as well as enrollment in clinical placement as part of experiential education, which also strengthens antibiotic knowledge.

Students who expressed satisfaction with antimicrobial education were more likely to have a positive attitude, while those who were dissatisfied were more likely to engage in self-medication practice. Similar findings were observed in China, where medical students who perceived their antimicrobial education as useful had better antibiotic knowledge than those who did not (Yang et al. 2016). In addition, in a recent study among healthcare professionals in Colombia, perceived adequacy of university preparation for appropriate antibiotic use was a predictor of positive attitudes and practices toward antibiotic use (Taborda et al. 2024). This emphasizes the need to integrate infectious disease guidelines into undergraduate education programs to ensure optimal preparation for prudent antibiotic use and mitigate the impact of antibiotic misuse.

From a public health perspective, enhancing awareness among healthcare professionals and the general population of AMR is part of the solution to the growing AMR crisis (Horvat et al. 2022). Governmental initiatives to strictly regulate antibiotic dispensing in the community are equally important to combat resistance. In addition, integration of interdisciplinary clinical placements into the curriculum to enhance collaboration, teamwork, and knowledge sharing through workshops, case-based learning, and group discussions is important for improving knowledge retention (Homsí et al. 2025). Furthermore, the inclusion of an antimicrobial stewardship module and clinical training in infectious diseases, as requested by students, is of paramount importance for strengthening their antibiotic knowledge (Abdelkarim et al. 2024). Future research that assesses the impact of utilizing active learning

methods such as e-learning, simulation-based teaching, and serious gaming, such as AntibioGame, in antimicrobial education, particularly with regard to knowledge retention, is recommended (Tsopra et al. 2020).

This is the first study in Iraq to include an in-depth assessment of knowledge, perceptions, and attitudes regarding antibiotic use and resistance among medical and pharmacy students during their clinical training years. However, the study has certain limitations that should be considered when interpreting study findings. First, inherent in the study design, it was not possible to estimate the response rate. However, the sample size was comparable to that used in recent studies (Horvat et al. 2022; Nukaly et al. 2024; Alshehri and Khawagi 2025). Second, initial dissemination within pharmacy school, online recruitment, and differential engagement across disciplines may have influenced the study sample composition. Thus, students with greater knowledge of infectious diseases may be more inclined to participate; this might lead to selection bias and result in an overestimation of the antibiotic knowledge rate. However, the findings align well with the existing literature. Lastly, the majority of participants from universities in Baghdad may limit the generalizability of the findings to other areas of the country. Thus, study findings can be considered informative rather than population-definitive. In addition, thresholds used to define adequate knowledge and positive attitude were literature-informed rather than intrinsically validated. Future studies that employ stratified sampling methodology are recommended to enhance generalizability to a broader student population.

Conclusion

This study indicates significant gaps in the knowledge, attitude, and practice of pharmacy and medical students toward antibiotic use and resistance. While more than half demonstrated adequate knowledge and positive attitude, three in five practiced self-medication, and a significant proportion believed that antibiotics are effective for treating the common cold and sore throat. Furthermore, less than half were familiar with the term antimicrobial stewardship. GPA and avoidance of self-medication were key predictors of adequate knowledge. Study year was a predictor of adequate knowledge and positive attitude, while satisfaction with antimicrobial education significantly predicted attitude and self-medication practice. This highlights the need to integrate antimicrobial stewardship principles into curricula to combat the growing threat of antibiotic resistance.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The author has declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and was approved by the institutional review board of the College of Pharmacy, Mustansiriyah University, Baghdad, Iraq (reference no. 201). Prior to participation, informed consent was obtained from all participants. The consent form explained the study's aims and objectives and informed students of the estimated time required to complete the survey, emphasizing that participation is voluntary and anonymous.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Ola contributes to the conception and design, the analysis and interpretation of data, and the writing and revision of the manuscript for important intellectual content.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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